

Forensic constraints on the tent-site trauma in the Dyatlov incident

(Matters Arising)

Caroline Detry

Independent Researcher, Namur, Belgium

Correspondence: caroline.detry@gmail.com

Introduction

Gaume and Puzrin (2021) proposed that a delayed slab avalanche at the tent caused “severe but non-lethal” injuries, and compelled the group to descend toward the forest¹. According to the 1959 case files, four of its members (Dubinina, Thibeaux-Brignolle, Zolotaryov and Kolevatov), exhibiting varying injury severity², were found in a ravine, nearby a cedar tree³ roughly 1.5 km downslope from the tent⁴. Here we re-evaluate the proposed avalanche-descent sequence using the 1959 autopsy reports and sworn testimony of the forensic examiner B.A. Vozrozhdenniy⁵ as the primary source for all medical and functional constraints, supplemented only by standard physiological frameworks and an empirical model to quantify walking time.

The survival windows and the functional capacities documented in the forensic record are incompatible with the baseline model-derived time required to traverse the ~1.5 km descent. This discrepancy is methodological rather than interpretative: it follows directly from the functional limits documented in the forensic records and persists across the full range of plausible walking-time estimates, irrespective of the modelling approach used to compute them. Forensic survival and functional capacity constitute hard empirical constraints that any physical model must satisfy; they reflect documented physiological limits and cannot be overridden by mechanical force-tolerance estimates alone.

Forensic Analysis

All medical and functional constraints are drawn directly from the 1959 autopsy reports and the sworn testimony of forensic examiner B.A. Vozrozhdenniy.

Standard trauma physiology (e.g. ATLS) is used solely as a descriptive framework to characterise the physiological implications of these documented injuries. It introduces no new assumptions and does not extend beyond what is explicit in the 1959 record.

Dubinina

Autopsy: bilateral rib fractures (R2-R5 right, R2-R7 left), massive ~1.5 L haemothorax, myocardial contusion².

Vozrozhdenniy's testimony: Dubinina "died 10-20 minutes after the trauma", "she could have been conscious " and her condition represented "complicated traumatic shock resulting from bilateral rib fractures followed by internal haemorrhaging into the pleural cavity"⁵;

Standard trauma physiology: a haemothorax of this magnitude corresponds to Class III haemorrhagic shock, arising directly from the bilateral rib fractures, which simultaneously produce ventilatory compromise. The fractures and the resulting intrathoracic haemorrhage constitute a single traumatic complex ; the autopsy provides no support for delayed or staged progression. Sustained exertion over 20-21 minutes is physiologically incompatible with Class III shock, whose cardiopulmonary failure is accelerated by the cold exposure.

Thibeaux-Brignolle

Autopsy: depressed multi-fragment basilar skull fracture with extensive comminution and massive cerebral oedema².

Vozrozhdenniy's testimony: after such a trauma Thibeaux-Brignolle "would have had a severe concussion, that is, he would have been in an unconscious state", that "moving him would have been difficult and, close to the end, movement would not have been possible even if he had been helped. He could only have been carried or dragged", while possibly showing "signs of life for 2-3 hours".

Standard trauma physiology: basilar skull fractures with extensive comminution can preserve residual cardiorespiratory activity while eliminating voluntary motor capacity, consistent with Vozrozhdenniy's description.

Transporting an unconscious adult under such conditions would produce widened, irregular or overlapping track patterns, none of which were reported in the 1959 search record .

Zolotaryov

Autopsy: right-sided flail chest (ribs II-VI fractured along mid-sternal and mid-axillary lines) with ~1 L haemothorax².

Standard trauma physiology: this injury pattern constitutes a unified thoracic trauma complex: chest wall dissociation produces paradoxical respiration, pulmonary contusion and hypoxemia, while the haemothorax produces Class II haemorrhagic shock. Flail chest physiology does not permit sustained exertion ; the ventilatory deficit results from mechanical loss of chest wall integrity, not from the pain or individual tolerance. Cold exposure accelerates the lethal triad of hypothermia, coagulopathy and acidosis. Even brief exertion aggravates hypoxemia ; no form of sustained human locomotion can physiologically compensate for these combined deficits.

Kolevatov

Vozrozhdenniy attributed death to hypothermia. No ante-mortem trauma impairing locomotion documented.

Walking time estimation

According to the 1959 case files, the cedar and the nearby ravine lie ~1.5 km downslope from the tent³. Walking speed was estimated using a validated empirical model for off-road locomotion, solely to quantify the descent duration implied by the 1959 scenario.

No dated photographic evidence documents the state of the snow surface near the tent during the night of the incident. The only contemporaneous primary description is Chernyshev's 1959 testimony, noting tracks appearing as "elevations in the form of bars" with "toes imprinted"⁸. This morphology indicates a deformable, non-consolidated snowpack rather than a hard-packed surface. Within the locomotion model such deformability corresponds to heavy-obstruction and represents the most conservative classification supported by the record.

For a mean slope of 9.4° (see Supplementary Information) and heavy-obstruction terrain, the empirical walking-speed model predicts a velocity of 4.2 km/h. Accordingly, the ~1.5 km traverse requires approximately 20-21 minutes for an uninjured group. A five-segment sensitivity analysis is provided as Supplementary Information, yielding a traversal time consistent with this baseline.

No adjustment is applied for injuries, hypothermia or lack of footwear, as no empirical locomotion data exist for such conditions. This does not introduce uncertainty: any impairment would be expected to prolong the descent rather than shorten it.

Integration of Forensic and Locomotion Constraints

The 1959 track record describes 8-9 distinct sets of walking footprints without indications of widening, irregular gaits or dragging. No trace evidence supports the transport of injured adults. Taken together, the forensic constraints (loss of consciousness, haemorrhagic shock, flail chest physiology), survival windows and locomotion requirements are internally incompatible with a tent-site origin of the thoracic and cranial trauma. This discrepancy arises from integrating two independent components:

- (1) the functional limitations documented explicitly in the 1959 forensic records, interpreted within standard, non-controversial trauma physiology; and
- (2) a baseline model-derived estimate of the time required for an uninjured group to traverse the ~1.5 km descent, quantified using a contemporary empirical walking-speed model.

The physiological constraints themselves derive solely from the autopsies and testimony ; the locomotion model is used only to estimate the duration of the descent, not to interfere or modify any medical conclusion.

Across all plausible parameter choices consistent with the 1959 description of a deformable, non-consolidated snow surface, the traversal time remains comparable to (or exceeds) the upper bound of Dubinina's documented survival windows, and remains incompatible with the immediate unconsciousness of Thibeaux-Brignolle and the ventilatory/circulatory impairment described in Zolotaryov.

Thus the incompatibility does not depend on a specific model but on the consistency of forensic constraints with the minimum feasible descent duration.

Conclusion

The avalanche-initiated sequence proposed by Gaume & Puzrin does not satisfy the survival-time and functional capacity constraints established in the 1959 forensic records. Under the documented physiological limitations, the thoracic and cranial trauma cannot originate at the tent while still permitting completion of a 1.5 km descent. Conversely if the descent occurred before the trauma, the tent-site slab-release model does not account for these injuries. The scenario therefore contains an internal methodological inconsistency: its physical trigger cannot be reconciled with the physiological capacities of the victims as documented in 1959. This Matters Arising does not propose an alternative mechanism ; its scope is limited to assessing the internal consistency of the tent-site impact hypothesis under the constraints of the contemporaneous forensic evidence.

References

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Declarations

Data availability

All data used are from publicly available sources as cited.

The ArcticDEM dataset is available from the Polar Geospatial Center (<https://www.pgc.umn.edu/data/arcticdem/>)

The coordinate data generated for the descent profile reconstruction in this study are provided as Supplementary Data 1.

Competing interests

The author declares no competing interests.

Author contributions

Caroline Detry is the sole author of this work.